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Online Intercultural Exchange: A case study in Work and Organizational Psychology

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Acquiring intercultural competences is critical in order to avoid prejudice and increase tolerance in the global workforce. This case study describes and evaluates a learning experience designed to develop intercultural competences. Cross-cultural leadership theories were incorporated into the syllabus of a Work and Organizational Psychology (WOP) course. Students applied these theories while gaining international exposure through Online Intercultural Exchanges (OIE). Students from the University of Valencia (Spain) and the University Centre of Brasília (Brazil) participated in the exchange. The sample was composed of 22 undergraduate psychology students who worked in international pairs to address cross-cultural leadership. Results showed that students gained knowledge about cross-cultural leadership, developed intercultural competences, and evaluated the learning experience as satisfactory. These findings encourage the use of OIE to incorporate cross-cultural aspects in WOP.

Keywords: Online Intercultural Exchange; Cross-cultural Leadership; Work and Organizational Psychology; Virtual Exchange

Introduction

Intercultural competences have gained relevance in today's globalized labour market. It is important to prepare professionals for international careers (Gabrenya & Yan, 2014) and multicultural workplaces in order to avoid prejudice and increase tolerance (Knight & de Wit, 2018). Additionally, Work and Organizational Psychology (WOP) practitioners should be able to extend domestic WOP consulting activities (e.g., leadership development) to international contexts. Thus, in their subjects, WOP academics should incorporate contents and supporting activities that enhance intercultural competences (Griffith et al., 2012; Griffith & Armon, 2014). Currently, specific guidance about how to do this is limited (Griffith & Armon, 2014).

Online Intercultural Exchanges (OIE) provide the opportunity to gain intercultural competences via online discussions (Commander et al., 2016; Ryan & Gelfand, 2012). Given that less than 5% of students worldwide participate in study abroad programs (Marinoni, 2019), OIE emerges as an alternative that provides students with international experience without costly and difficult mobility.

This case study describes and assesses a learning activity designed to develop WOP students' intercultural competences, first, by using a cross-cultural approach to study leadership, and, second, by providing students with international exposure through OIE. Undergraduate psychology students from the University of Valencia (UV Spain) and the University Centre of Brasília (UniCEUB Brazil) collaborated online with a common goal: to acquire and apply knowledge about cross-cultural leadership through direct contact and structured interactions with international peers.

The acquisition of intercultural competences through OIE

OIE refers to *'the engagement of groups of students in online intercultural interaction and collaboration with partner classes from other cultural contexts or geographical locations under the guidance of educators and/or expert facilitators'* (Lewis & O'Dowd, 2016, p. 15). It emerges as an appropriate strategy to develop intercultural competences (European Commission, 2018), defined as *'a set of cognitive, affective, and behavioural skills and characteristics that support effective and appropriate interaction in a variety of cultural contexts'* (Bennett, 2009; p. 97).

Despite this, the use of OIE in higher education is limited (O'Dowd, 2018) and fails to address OIE pedagogical principles. Previous research either neglects OIE's expected learning outcomes (Wang, 2011), or it does not provide details about how to attain them (Gabrenya & Yan, 2014; Gonzalez-Perez et al., 2014; Lindner, 2016). Other studies focus on practical aspects of launching OIE (e.g., recruiting and selecting partner universities) (Taras et al., 2014).

Only a few exceptions (Duus & Cooray, 2014; Taras et al., 2013) provide guidelines about OIE activities. However, these studies have been carried out in the areas of international business and marketing, and the generalizability of their results is uncertain. For example, Taras et al.'s (2013) study is based on a large sample of graduate and undergraduate students who participated in OIEs via text-based communication media throughout different academic years. Over the years, OIE characteristics have changed (e.g., assignments, team composition, participant countries, or modes of collaboration). Thus, it is difficult to identify what conditions foster the postulated learning outcomes most.

Our study extends previous research in several ways. It introduces OIE in the field of WOP, where there is a need for specific guidelines for internationalizing courses (Griffith & Armon, 2014). Additionally, it goes a step further by incorporating cross-cultural leadership theories in the course syllabus. We provide the necessary theoretical foundations and guided reflection in the classroom to appreciate and interpret similarities and differences across cultures. The application of cross-cultural knowledge and the development of intercultural competences form the core of the activity. This requires incorporating an international perspective in the course syllabus that is shared by the universities participating in the exchange (O'Dowd, 2018). This approach differs from a similar one adopted in international business and marketing. Here, developing a business proposal is the main goal, and the acquisition of intercultural competences is a means to an end (e.g., increased effectiveness in international virtual projects, ability to respond to a real-life business challenge) (Lindner, 2016; O'Dowd, 2018). This approach does not require the introduction of cross-cultural content in the course syllabus, and intercultural competences are assumed to be cultivated during the development of the business proposal. Moreover, our case study describes the learning activity in detail, so that it can be replicated by others, thus contributing to the accumulation of knowledge. In addition, it allows us to explain the knowledge gained and ascertain how this experience might be transferrable to other learning situations.

Finally, our study involves a Latin American country, where OIEs should be encouraged. In these countries, outbound and inbound mobility is among the lowest in the world, and study abroad programs are continuously threatened by economic and political instability (Gacel-Ávila, 2018).

Case study and methods

Course design

The course design combined face-to-face teaching in each home country and OIE engagement with peer students in the other University, in addition to students' own work. Students interacted outside the classroom through both synchronous (e.g., videoconferencing) and asynchronous (e.g., email) tools. The stages of the learning activity are described below.

Face-to-face project presentation. The instructor explained the purpose of the project, the expected learning outcomes, and the assignments to be carried out. Participation was voluntary, and the final assignment received a maximum grade of 1 point.

Students' self-study. Students read two book chapters from a critical perspective (Gil & Martí, 2011; Northouse, 2016). Our aim was to raise students' awareness of universal and context-dependent aspects of leadership prototypes. Leadership prototypes refer to common characteristics generally attributed to a leader by a community or group of people. These prototypes are likely to differ across cultures and influence individuals' behaviours (Den Hartog et al., 1999).

Face-to-face debate. Students in each home university discussed international research on leadership prototypes associated with the different cultural clusters (e.g., GLOBE Project). Students' assumptions about 'others', but also about their own culture, were challenged. For instance, students were asked if they feel identified with prevalent stereotypes, or the main cultural characteristics identified in transcultural research about their own country.

Design of the interview. The interview guide was designed based on GLOBE literature. Open questions were encouraged to avoid biases and stereotypes, acknowledging that

cultures and leadership styles are not monolithic within countries. Interview guides were revised by the lecturers during tutorials.

Synchronous virtual exchange with peers in the other university. Students worked in randomly-assigned pairs (one from each university). They were asked to interview each other using synchronous voice or video call to ensure live interaction as well as proximity and closeness. Microsoft Teams and institutional Google Meet were available; however, most of them used videophone tools.

Delivery of the assignment. Each student turned in an individual assignment (2000-4000 words) that included a theoretical framework, method, results, discussion, conclusions, and references. Four levels of achievement were established (fail, pass, good, and excellent) and qualitative feedback was provided to students on the strengths and areas of improvement of their work.

Students' evaluation of the learning experience. Students evaluated the learning experience. They reported what they valued most, their perceived accomplishment of the learning goals, and how the OIE learning activity could be improved.

Participants

The sample was composed of 22 undergraduate psychology students (third year) enrolled in the Organizational Psychology course. Ten students pertained to the University Centre of Brasília (UniCEUB, Brazil), a private institution located in the Federal Capital, Brasilia. The campus is located in a peripheral zone of the city (25 km from the city centre), and it attracts middle-class students. All the students were Brazilian, and most of them were female (N=9) and White (N=6) (2 were Black, 1 indigenous, and 1 mixed race). Two of them had previously lived abroad.

Twelve students pertained to the University of Valencia (UV, Spain). The UV is

a public university focused on teaching and research in most academic fields, and it is located in the urban setting of the large city of Valencia (Spain). Ten students were female (N=10), and all 12 students were middle-class White Spaniards.

Data collection and analyses

A mixed-methods approach (quantitative and qualitative data) was used to assess knowledge about cross-cultural leadership, intercultural competences, and satisfaction with the activity. Two data sources were employed (lecturers and students).

Qualitative Measures

First, lecturers evaluated the students' cross-cultural leadership knowledge and its practical application by assessing the individual assignments. The following aspects were considered: understanding of cross-cultural leadership research (e.g., leadership dimensions identified in the GLOBE project), its practical application (design of the interview guide and interpretation of the results), critical thinking about leadership prototypes, and reflections on the practical implications of cross-cultural aspects for WOP professionals. The specific criteria used to evaluate the individual assignments are available on request from the corresponding author.

Moreover, we obtained self-reported qualitative data. On the individual assignment, students critically reflected on the OIE project and how to improve the activity. Moreover, after submitting the final assignment, they answered an anonymous online survey that included the following open-ended question: *'Please, explain what you expected from this learning activity and what it finally brought you'*. Self-reported qualitative data were analysed through content analysis.

Quantitative Measures

Quantitative data were obtained from the anonymous online survey, which is available upon request from the corresponding author. Preliminary descriptive analyses and independent-samples t-tests to compare the results obtained in the different universities were carried out. The questionnaire included the following heading for the cognitive processes, intercultural competences, and interest and awareness scale: *'Please, indicate to what extent the cross-cultural leadership project has helped you to ...'*. The response scale ranged from 1 (Strongly disagree) to 4 (Strongly agree).

Cognitive processes. An eight-item measure was developed by the research team following the revision of the Bloom's Taxonomy by Anderson et al. (2001). These cognitive processes enable learning, and their complexity ranges from *'understand and remember'* (3 items), *'apply'* (2 items), and *'analyse'* (2 items) to *'create and evaluate'* (1 item). A sample item was *'Analyse leadership from different theoretical approaches'* (Analyse).

Intercultural competences were assessed using a three-item scale (e.g., *'Acquire useful skills for working in multicultural teams'*).

Interest and awareness were measured with a two-item scale (e.g., *'Increase your interest in learning about other cultures'*).

Satisfaction with the learning activity. Students answered a 10-item scale asking them to what extent they were satisfied with different aspects of the learning process (e.g., the skills acquired). Students answered using a 5-point Likert scale (1= Completely dissatisfied, 5= Completely satisfied).

Self-reported performance. A single-item scale was used: *'I am satisfied with my involvement in the project'*. The response scale ranged from 1 (Strongly disagree) to 5 (Strongly agree).

Results

Qualitative results

Cross-cultural leadership knowledge and its practical application. Formative feedback during the learning process and assessment of the individual assignments showed that students gained cross-cultural leadership knowledge and were able to apply it in practice. Overall, students understood universal and context-related leadership behaviours described in the GLOBE project, and they identified examples in their interviews. They adopted a critical approach, showing awareness of the need to combine different perspectives when addressing cultural issues, as well as the influence of stereotypes and prejudice. The task appeared to be challenging but achievable. Some students had the opportunity to experience the challenge of transforming the recently acquired knowledge on cross-cultural leadership theories into the design of a semi-structured interview. Spanish students suggested that it would be useful if lecturers provided students with a pre-designed survey or an interview guide. However, we recognized that designing their own interview guide would enrich their learning experience because it requires complex cognitive processes such as creating, evaluating, and turning theory into practice. In contrast to the Spanish students, the Brazilians valued the autonomy involved in developing their own interview guide based on their interests in leadership.

Intercultural competences. Self-reported qualitative measures indicated that the OIE supported the development of intercultural understanding (cognitive domain) and sensitivity (affective domain). Students learned about a different culture and shared different views on leadership (Intercultural understanding -cognitive domain), as noted in the following statements:

'I met a person from another culture who shared with me her way of seeing things, I learned from her, and it was a much more enjoyable task than if I had had to rely on theory alone to draw my conclusions'

'We have been talking about the different foods, public holidays, and traditions that exist in each country...'

'I loved having the opportunity to talk to people from another continent and to talk about psychology and leadership in other countries'

Students enjoyed the interaction and showed interest, respect, and empathy toward other cultures. They also acknowledged their subjective personal experiences with cultural differences (Intercultural sensitivity -affective domain). Some examples on this topic are:

'(...) we can understand other people's experiences, as well as the impressions a person living in another country can have about the country where you live, which is really interesting'

*'I liked being able to get to know another culture, and it has made me interested in it'
'Besides, he told me about the inequalities that people experience in Brazil. I think that no one in the world should live like this'*

Overall satisfaction and evaluation of the learning experience. Overall, students were satisfied with the learning experience, describing it as: *'Interesting', 'Dynamic', 'Motivating', 'Enjoyable', 'Novel', 'Enriching', and 'Incredible'*. As one person stated: *'Certainly, international activities must continue to be provided'*. Moreover, students reported that their expectations were exceeded, as illustrated in the following statements:

'I thought that the work was going to be more "tedious" due to having to do it remotely with a person I did not know, but thanks to the fact that my partner was as involved as I was in the project, it was very enjoyable and rewarding'

Furthermore, the learning experience contributed to students' personal growth, as highlighted in the following comments:

'(...) beyond the knowledge about the organizational culture, a very positive life experience'

'The experiences we have shared have shown me what kind of leader I would like to be when the time comes'

Students also acknowledged that the OIE was an opportunity to practice other languages (e.g., *'This work has allowed me to practice English'*) and establish interpersonal

relationships with students from other countries (e.g., *'I know that I will have contact with a person that I would never have known otherwise'*), which contributes to improving the affective component of intercultural competences (Pettigrew, 1998). When the activity was presented, these aspects caused concern in some students (e.g., lack of linguistic competence, meeting a new person). However, after the activity ended, they valued these challenges as an opportunity (e.g., *'I was a bit concerned about having to talk by video call with someone I didn't know, in addition to the issue of the language.'*).

Quantitative results

Overall, reliability indexes were satisfactory. Bivariate correlations for all the variables are presented in Table 1.

--Insert about here Table 1--

Cognitive processes. Results showed that average scores for all the cognitive processes were above the mid-point of the scale (See Table 1). *'Apply'* and *'Create and evaluate'* obtained the highest scores.

Intercultural competences. The average score on interest and awareness was close to the highest point on the scale. The OIE raised interest in learning about other cultures and awareness of the relevance of cultural differences in better understanding organizational phenomena. Moreover, it helped students to develop intercultural competences to work in a multicultural environment.

Overall satisfaction and evaluation of participation in the OIE. Students were very satisfied with the learning experience and with their own performance. Overall satisfaction showed the highest mean score followed by self-reported performance.

Independent samples t-tests comparing Brazilian and Spanish students revealed statistically significant differences in the cognitive process *'Analyse'*, $t(20)=2.65$,

$p=.015$. Spanish students ($M=3.75$, $SD=.34$) reported significantly higher scores than the Brazilian students ($M=3.25$, $SD=.54$). No differences were found in any of the other evaluated aspects, showing that, in general terms, the OIE had a similar influence in both groups of students.

Discussion

This case study aimed to describe and assess an OIE experience between two countries in higher education in WOP. The learning activity was designed to enhance the intercultural competences of undergraduate psychology students in Brazil and Spain while they learned about a shared topic from their syllabus, that is, cross-cultural leadership.

Both qualitative and quantitative results showed that the OIE was satisfactory for students and promoted the development of intercultural competences, which is congruent with previous research (e.g., Taras et al., 2013; 2014). Lecturers' assessments of individual assignments revealed that students achieved the learning objectives with good results. Students consistently reported that the learning activity stimulated the broad array of cognitive processes relevant for learning: from understand and remember to the more complex skills of create and evaluate (Bloom et al., 1956).

This study extends previous research by supporting the use of OIE in the field of WOP in higher education. Additionally, it expands previous studies that failed to provide details about OIE activities that support the development of intercultural competences (e.g., Gonzalez-Pérez et al., 2014). As a case study, this work provides contextualized information about how the OIE was developed and assessed, and it facilitates replication and transference to other situations. Finally, it contributes to the internationalization of the WOP curriculum by incorporating cross-cultural topics (e.g., cross-cultural leadership) into undergraduate courses.

This study has relevant practical implications. First, our results suggest that OIE might help students to prepare for multicultural working environments. Second, the knowledge gained provides future WOP professionals with a theoretical basis for challenging predominant Western theoretical models of leadership that might not be generalizable to other regions, such as Latin American countries (Gabrenya, & Yan, 2014).

Third, the results encourage other lecturers in higher education in general, and in WOP in particular, to incorporate OIE into their subjects taking into account several aspects. First, recruitment and selection of potential partners for the OIE should consider learning goals established in their respective syllabi, students' profiles, and the academic calendar at each university. The OIE should be enriching for both partner universities. Moreover, academic calendars and students' workload in the different stages of the OIE should be compatible to facilitate collaboration. Along these lines, the weight of the OIE exchange in the final mark should be similar. In this case study students obtained a maximum grade of 1 point in both countries; however, based in our experience, we recommend increasing this value because it is a demanding learning activity for students.

Second, it is very important to clarify the students' expectations about the OIE activity from the very beginning, framing OIE as a teaching intervention that promotes the internationalization of education and the acquisition of intercultural competence. In this way, expectations about learning goals and how to achieve them are clear. In this regard, students should have a clear understanding of the importance of doing the activity through *synchronous virtual exchanges with peers in the other university*. We noticed that the time difference might lead some students to take shortcuts to get the task done, such as performing the task by e-mail. *Synchronous virtual exchanges* should

be encouraged because they are more likely to enhance intercultural competences, in terms of cognitive, affective, and behavioural skills. Live interaction might lead to developing a more in-depth approach to universal and context-dependent aspects of leadership prototypes, creating affective ties with “*others*”, and changing behaviours such as communication styles based on immediate and spontaneous feedback.

Third, based on the students’ suggestions, after the *synchronous virtual exchange with peers in the other university*, it would be useful for them to share their findings with their classmates (e.g., debate or round table). They suggested that sharing this information would help them to make sense of the interview results. It would also provide an opportunity for instructors to stimulate discussion about context-dependent aspects of leadership prototypes, as well as ingroup and outgroup assumptions and stereotypes.

Fourth, it is advisable to devote time in the classroom to analysing and interpreting conflicts and misunderstandings in light of cultural differences (e.g., different communication styles). The mere exposure to diversity does not ensure the development of intercultural competences, and it might even reinforce stereotypes (Villar-Onrubia & Rajpal, 2016).

Finally, it is noteworthy that the students participating in this case study spontaneously created spaces (e.g., WhatsApp group) to share resources and recommendations. Their interaction was not limited to the specific activity, but rather it continued throughout the course on a more informal basis. This suggests that the students valued and enjoyed their interactions with peers from other universities. Thus, we encourage instructors to design other OIEs that enable more frequent interactions by combining different tools (e.g., forums or presentations) and methodologies (e.g., problem-based projects, capstone activities).

The small sample size of this study and the limited use of objective indicators of students' learning make it difficult to draw strong conclusions about the benefits of OIEs. Future research should replicate this study in several groups or multiple times in order to provide stronger empirical evidence. We also encourage future researchers to assess students' learning using objective indicators of intercultural competences measured before and after the teaching intervention. They should also broaden their scope by measuring the influence of OIEs on digital competences or other relevant outcomes (e.g., intercultural sensitivity -respect for cultural differences-, global citizenship -participation in global movements). In countries such as Brazil and Spain, where students' linguistic competences are limited, it would also be worthwhile to assess students' perceived self-efficacy about interacting with others in a foreign language, as well as their willingness to complete their studies abroad before and after the teaching intervention.

Overall, future research should shed light on the way OIE might contribute to the internationalization of education and complement other internationalization strategies, such as study abroad programs. However, even though OIE activities are meant to overcome some of the barriers to internationalization (e.g. travel costs), other barriers still prevail. Differences in access to digital technologies (e.g., computer, WIFI) and linguistic abilities might still hamper '*internationalization for all*', especially in less developed countries (e.g. East and Central Africa) (Naicker et al., 2021). Nonetheless, this experience also shows that OIE can be successfully applied through access to mobile phones and free-of-charge applications and in the context of sister languages.

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Table 1. Descriptive statistics, alpha coefficients, and correlations

Variable	M	SD	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
1. Understand and remember	3.59	.42	(.70)							
2. Apply	3.77	.37	.04	(.67)						
3. Analyse	3.52	.50	.35	.03	(.62)					
4. Create and evaluate	3.77	.43	.43*	.11	.14	--				
5. Intercultural competences	3.58	.48	.56**	.06	.47*	.28	(.74)			
6. Interest and awareness	3.91	.25	-.29	.02	-.17	-.20	-.07	(.62)		
7. Students' satisfaction	4.63	.32	.43*	.24	.31	.19	.52*	.33	(.70)	
8. Self-reported performance	4.45	.80	.11	.37	.21	.18	-.01	.22	.34	--

Note: *p < 05 and **p < 01. Alpha coefficients between brackets